

Boletín informativo CTK 2017 / CTK Newsletter 2017

ANA-CAROLINA GUTIÉRREZ-XIVILLÉ*

Workshops

2. Internationaler Doktoranden-Workshop zur Kant-Forschung	
Fecha:	21-23/4/2016
Lugar:	Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg
Información:	<p>– Organizadores: Kant-Gesellschaft Landesforschungsschwerpunkt „Aufklärung-Religion-Wissen. Transformationen des Religiösen und des Rationalen“ (ARW) Immanuel-Kant-Forum (IKF) der Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg</p>
Keynote speakers:	Prof. Dr. Otfried Höffe (Tübingen), Prof. Dr. Dietmar Heidemann (Luxembourg), Prof. Dr. Kate Moran (Boston, z.Z. Jena) und Prof. Dr. Jens Timmermann (St. Andrews).
<p>Ziel des Workshops ist es, den wissenschaftlichen Austausch zwischen Doktorandinnen und Doktoranden, die eine Dissertation zur Philosophie Kants anfertigen, sowie bereits etablierten Forscherinnen und Forschern anzuregen und zu fördern. Der Workshop gibt den Teilnehmerinnen und Teilnehmern die Gelegenheit, ihre Projekte in 30-minütigen Vorträgen mit anschließender Diskussion zu präsentieren.</p>	
Contacto:	<p>Prof. Dr. Heiner F. Klemme Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg Seminar für Philosophie / Immanuel-Kant-Forum Emil-Abderhalden-Str. 26-27 D-06099 Halle (Saale) http://www.phil.uni-halle.de/immanuel-kant-forum_ikf/ http://www.exzellenz-netzwerk-arw.uni-halle.de/</p>
CFP:	<p>Deadline: 31/01/2016 Einsendungen per Email (als PDF-Anhang) in deutscher oder englischer Sprache von geeigneten Exposés (max. 750 Worte) sowie einer Kurzvita werden erbeten an Prof. Dr. Heiner F. Klemme (Heiner.Klemme@phil.uni-halle.de). Aus den Einsendungen wird eine Auswahl von sieben Beiträgen getroffen. Die Hotelkosten der Vortragenden werden übernommen, Reisekosten in Höhe von bis zu € 500,-. Die Teilnahme an dem Workshop steht darüber hinaus allen Interessierten offen. Um vorherige Anmeldung beim Veranstalter wird gebeten.</p>

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Kant, Maria von Herbert, and Early Modern Women Philosophers Third Carinthian Workshop on Topics in Early Modern Philosophy to Kant	
Fecha:	21 – 22/10/2016
Lugar:	Institute of Philosophy, University of Klagenfurt K 0.01 (Stiftungssall, Servicegebäude) Universitätsstr. 65-67 Klagenfurt 9020 Austria
Keynote speakers:	Martha Bolton (Rutgers University), Rae Langton (Cambridge University), Ursula Renz (University of Klagenfurt), Bernhard Ritter (University of Klagenfurt)
<p>The Third Carinthian EMP-Kant Workshop focusses on the role of women philosophers in the early modern period until Kant, thereby drawing attention to the Herbert circle in Klagenfurt, where, as K. L. Fernow once wrote enthusiastically to Reinhold, also the women were 'Selbstdenkerinnen', i.e., autonomous thinkers. The women Fernow was referring to were the von Dreer sisters and Maria von Herbert (1769-1803) who today is known for a singular exchange of letters with Immanuel Kant. It is only until relatively recently that her letters have inspired a lively philosophical debate in the English-written literature on Kant, while German-speaking scholars have been focussing on the role of the Herbert circle in the history of Enlightenment. The Third Carinthian Workshop wishes to encourage a philosophical exchange centred on the figure of Maria von Herbert, but it also welcomes submissions on other women philosophers of the period.</p>	
Contacto:	Prof. Ursula Renz, University of Klagenfurt
CFP:	Deadline: 10/08/2016 There are still a few more slots open for speakers. Prospective speakers are kindly requested to send a note of interest and an abstract of 250 to 500 words.

Kant-Kurs: Kant über das freie Spiel der Erkenntnisvermögen (§ 9 der KU)	
Fecha:	24 – 25/11/2016
Lugar:	Universität Siegen
Keynote speakers:	Prof. Rachel Zuckert, Ph.D.(Northwestern University) und Prof. Dr. Dieter Schönecker (Universität Siegen)
<p>Der Workshop konzentriert sich auf § 9 der "Kritik der Urteilskraft", in dem Kant das freie und harmonische Spiel der Erkenntnisvermögen einführt. Als ‚Schlüssel‘ zur "Analytik des Schönen" ist dieser Paragraph von zentraler Bedeutung für ein profundes Verständnis der Kantischen Ästhetik.</p> <p>Die Kurse und Tagungen des ZetKIK zeichnen sich dadurch aus, dass es keine Vorträge oder Präsentationen gibt. Vielmehr werden wir den Kantischen Text gemeinsam sehr genau (kommentarisch) lesen und diskutieren.</p>	
CFP:	<p>Der Kurs richtet sich an fortgeschrittene Studierende, Doktoranden sowie Postdocs. Bewerbungen aus dem Ausland sind willkommen. Die Tagungssprache ist Englisch, die Fähigkeit, Kants Texte im deutschen Original zu lesen, wird allerdings vorausgesetzt.</p> <p>Alle Interessierten sind herzlich eingeladen, Bewerbungen inkl. CV und Empfehlungsschreiben bitte an dieter.schoenecker@uni-siegen.de zu senden.</p> <p>Deadline für Bewerbungen: 17. Okt. 2016.</p> <p>Reisestipendien stehen in begrenztem Umfang zur Verfügung.</p>

Kant's A-Deduction	
Fecha:	12 – 13/12/2016
Lugar:	Institute of Philosophy, KU Leuven HIW Kardinaal Mercierplein 2 Leuven 3000 Belgium
Información:	– Organizadores: Henny Blomme (KU Leuven), Arnaud Pelletier (Université Libre de Bruxelles), Joris Spigt (KU Leuven), Cody Staton (KU Leuven), Maarten Van Dyck (University of Ghent), Karin de Boer (KU Leuven), Geert van Eekert (University of Antwerp)
Keynote speakers:	Manfred Baum (University of Wuppertal), Corey W. Dyck (University of Western Ontario), Giuseppe Motta (Karl-Franzens-University Graz), Alexandra Newton (University of Illinois)
<p>For various reasons, many commentators tend to overlook the A-Deduction in favor of the 1787 edition. In contrast to that trend, this conference aims to interpret and assess Kant's A-Deduction on its own terms and shed light on important insights that are pivotal to the <i>Critique of Pure Reason</i> as a whole.</p> <p>The conference aims at stimulating fruitful exchanges between established scholars, young researchers, and PhD students.</p>	

CFP:	<p>Submission Deadline: September 15, 2016</p> <p>The Institute of Philosophy at the University of Leuven invites submissions for a conference dedicated to Kant's A-Deduction. Papers focusing on any aspect of the A-Deduction are welcome. Themes of papers may include, but are not limited to: the argumentative structure of the A-Deduction, key concepts of the A-Deduction, the roles of the various faculties, the historical context of the A-Deduction (especially in view of Kant's relationship to his contemporaries), and the fate of the A-Deduction (e.g. its reappraisal in the <i>Opus postumum</i>).</p> <p>Presentation time will be 25 minutes + 15 minutes for discussion.</p> <p>Abstracts (between 400 and 800 words) should be sent in MSWord as attachment to: a-deduction@kuleuven.be</p> <p>Abstracts have to be prepared for double-blind review by removing any identification details. The author's name, paper title, institutional position and affiliation, as well as contact information should be included in the body of the e-mail.</p> <p>Notification of acceptance by September 30, 2016.</p> <p>Please note that the organizers are unable to provide financial support for travel and lodging.</p> <p>For inquiries concerning this event, please write to: a-deduction@kuleuven.be https://hiw.kuleuven.be/ned/events/kants-a-deduction</p>
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Models of Human and Divine Intellect in Kant und Hegel: Intersections between Transcendental Philosophy and Rational Theology	
Fecha:	16 – 18/02/2017
Lugar:	Tübingen
Información:	– Organizadores: University of Tübingen
Keynote speakers:	Karin de Boer (KU Leuven), Paul Franks (Yale University), Stephen Houlgate (University of Warwick), Anton F. Koch (University of Heidelberg), Philipp Schwab (University of Freiburg), Henning Tegtmeier (KU Leuven).
<p>The workshop is funded by the University of Tübingen Excellence Initiative. In recent years there has been much debate about how and whether Hegel’s absolute idealism is either a radicalization or reversal of Kant’s transcendental idealism. At the centre of this debate are questions concerning the relation of logical space to reality, mind’s place in nature, the nature of conceptual content and the bounds of intelligibility. The workshop aims to explore these topics through the comparison of Kant’s and Hegel’s models of human and divine intellect. The workshop will combine keynote lectures and graduate student presentations.</p>	
CFP:	<p>We would like to invite PhD students to send an abstract of 500 words. Deadline: 15/09/2016 tuebingen.workshop@gmail.com We will notify you by 1st of October. If the paper is accepted, the full text deadline (3000 words) will be the 15th of January 2017.</p>

Congresos / Congresses

NAKS Pacific Study Group 2016	
North American Kant Society Pacific Study Group Meetings	
Fecha:	12 – 13/11/2016
Lugar:	Dept of Logic & Philosophy of Science, Dept of Philosophy University of California, Irvine 1517 SBSG Social & Behavioral Gateway #214 Irvine 92697-5100 United States
Información:	http://www.lps.uci.edu/newsevents/events/conferences.php – Organizadores: Jeremy Heis (University of California, Irvine) – Sponsor: North American Kant Society
All speakers:	R. Lanier Anderson (Stanford University), Jeanine Grenberg (St. Olaf College), Suzanne Love (University of Pittsburgh), Melissa McBay (Merritt University of New South Wales), Sheldon Smith (UCLA), Owen Ware (Simon Fraser University)
<u>Saturday, 11/12</u>	
1:00: Jeanine Grenberg (St. Olaf): “The Phenomenological Determination of Time and Feeling in Practical Cognitions”	
2:30: Sheldon Smith (UCLA): “Why does the later Kant think that there is substance throughout the space filled by matter?”	
4:00: R. Lanier Anderson (Stanford): “Transcendental Idealism as Formal Idealism”	
5:30: Business Meeting	
<u>Sunday, 11/13</u>	
9:00: Owen Ware (Simon Fraser): “A New Reading of Groundwork III”	
10:30: Suzanne Love (Pittsburgh): “Reciprocity, Citizenship, And Inequality In The Kantian State” (Winner of the Graduate Student Travel Stipend)	
12:00: Melissa McBay Merritt (New South Wales): “Respect, Love, and Individuals: Murdoch as a Guide to Kantian Ethics”	

Conceptions of Experience in the German Enlightenment between Wolff and Kant	
Fecha:	24 – 25/02/2017
Lugar:	University of Leuven
Información:	conceptionsofexperience@kuleuven.be – Organizadores: Karin de Boer (University of Leuven) Tinca Prunea-Bretonnet (University of Bucharest)
Keynote speakers:	Christian Leduc (Montréal) Arnaud Pelletier (Brussels) Anne-Lise Rey (Lille) Udo Thiel (Graz)
<p>The purpose of this conference is to analyze the various conceptions of experience at play in eighteenth-century German philosophy between Leibniz's death in 1716 and Kant's Critique of Pure Reason. During this period, the classical Aristotelian definition of experience as cognition of singulars – to some extent still present in Wolff – became confronted with the Baconian and Newtonian accounts of empirical knowledge. While most philosophers acknowledged the fundamental role of experience, they tried to accomodate the modern notions of experience to a view of cognition and science influenced by Wolffian metaphysics. The question as to the contribution of foundational metaphysical principles and empirical data to scientific knowledge was much discussed, as was the relationship between inner and outer experience, experience and thought, experience and judgment, experience and facts, experience and perception, experience and experiment, and perception and apperception. Challenging the historiographical opposition between empiricism and rationalism, the conference aims to explore the often ambivalent or fluid conceptions of experience at work in these debates, as well their influence on disciplines such as psychology and aesthetics.</p>	
CFP:	The conference aims at stimulating fruitful exchanges between established scholars, junior researchers, and PhD students. Presentation time will be 25 minutes + 20 minutes for discussion Deadline: 15/10/2016

The Many Faces of Kantian Freedom Spring Symposium	
Fecha:	22/4/2017
Lugar:	Department of Philosophy, University of Tennessee, Knoxville (United States)
Información:	http://philosophy.utk.edu/symposium/index.php – Organizadores: Markus Kohl (University of Tennessee, Knoxville) – Sponsors: Humanities Center, University of Tennessee, Knoxville
Keynote speakers:	Anne Margaret Baxley (Univ. of Washington in St. Louis) Markus Kohl (UT Knoxville) Andrews Reath (UC Riverside) Eric Watkins (UC San Diego)
<p>Kant refers to freedom as the "keystone" or the "cardinal point" of his entire philosophy. Kant is perhaps chiefly concerned with the freedom <i>of will</i> that we take ourselves to have as moral agents whose choices merit praise or blame. However, freedom (as well as the closely related idea of "spontaneity") plays a central role in other central areas of Kant's philosophy as well: in his epistemology, he holds that that we freely judge the natural world in response to sensible input; and his aesthetics famously centres around the notion of a "free play" of imagination and intellect. This colloquium brings together Kant scholars that have explored these different faces of Kantian freedom in their work, and thus it hopes to shed light on how the many different (metaphysical, ethical, epistemological, and aesthetic) dimensions of Kantian freedom are to be understood in their own right and in relation to each other.</p>	

VII. MULTILATERALES KANT-KOLLOQUIUM Kant und seine Kritiker / Kant and his critics / Kant et ses critiques	
Fecha:	28 – 30/04/2017
Lugar:	Löwengebäude & Melanchthonianum Universitätsplatz (Campus der Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg) Halle (Saale)
Información:	Prof. Dr. Heiner F. Klemme: Heiner.klemme@phil.uni-halle.de Dr. Antonino Falduto: Antonino.Falduto@phil.uni-halle.de Seminar für Philosophie / Immanuel-Kant-Forum Martin-Luther Universität Halle-Wittenberg – Organizadores: Immanuel-Kant-Forum (Seminar für Philosophie & „Interdisziplinäres Zentrum für die Erforschung der Europäischen Aufklärung“, IZEA) MartinLuther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg; Landesforschungsschwerpunkt „Aufklärung-Religion-Wissen“ (ARW);

CON-TEXTOS KANTIANOS

International Journal of Philosophy

N.º 5, Junio 2017, pp. 508-535

ISSN: 2386-7655

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.805921

	Kant-Gesellschaft e.V.; KantForschungsstelle der Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz; „Christian-Wolff-Gesellschaft für die Philosophie der Aufklärung“.
<p>FREITAG / FRIDAY, 28. APRIL 2017 08:45</p> <p>09:15 Eröffnung / Welcome.</p> <p>09:15 – 10:15 Eröffnungsvortrag / Opening lecture. Walter Ch. Zimmerli (HU Berlin), „Kant ‚behind our backs‘: Time and (time-)consciousness – today“</p> <p>Sektionen / Parallel sessions.</p> <p>10:25 – 11:15</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Corey Dyck (Univ. of Western Ontario, London / MLU HalleWittenberg) 'A serious blow to the Kantian Critique': Mendelssohn and the B Edition - Joel Thiago Klein (Univ. Rio Grande do Norte) Kant and Constant on Lying - Héctor Ferreiro (Pontificia Univ. Católica Argentina, Buenos Aires) La tesis kantiana del ser como posición y su crítica en la filosofía de Hegel <p>11:35 – 12:25</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reinhard Brandt (Philipps-Univ. Marburg) Lassen sich die ´Anmaaßungen der Vernunftkritik` gegen den Skeptizismus (AenesidemusSchulze) durch die Rechtsgrundlage der Transzendentalen Deduktion ("quid juris?") verteidigen? - Bas Tönissen (Univ. St. Andrews) The paradox of method in the Critique of Practical Reason: Kant's reply to H.A. Pistorius - Fiorella Tomassini (Univ. Buenos Aires) Die Einteilung der Rechtspflichten nach den Ulpian-Formeln <p>12:30 – 13:20</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sílvia Altmann (Univ. Rio Grande do Sul) Kant's answer to the Garve-Feder review in the Prolegomena - Valentina Dafne De Vita (MLU HalleWittenberg) Die zeitgenössischen Kritiker an Kants Pflichten gegen sich selbst - Gabriel Rivero (Univ. Mannheim) Kants Eigentumsrecht und seine Kritiker <p>14:20 – 15:10</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manfred Baum (Bergische Univ. Wuppertal) Über Kant und Eberhard - Paulo Rénatus Jesus (Univ. Lisboa) Kant et Lévinas sur l'origine de la loi morale - Gualtiero Lorini (TU Berlin) Recht, Sittlichkeit und Religion: eine politische Debatte? Einige Vergleichselemente zwischen Kant, Fichte und Hegel <p>15:25 – 16:15</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mirosław Żelanzy (Univ. Toruń) Maimon als Kritiker Kants Maimon's - Charles Feldhaus (Univ. Londrina) Kant, Schiller, Obligation and Chimerical Ethics - Emanuele Cafagna (Univ. Chieti-Pescara) Kant und die Gefahr des Determinismus <p>16:20 – 17:10</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hernán Pringe (Univ. Buenos Aires/Universidad Diego Portales, Santiago de Chile) Criticism of Kant's Doctrine of Mathematical Cognition and the Possibility of Metaphysics as a Science - Margit Ruffing (Johannes GutenbergUniv. Mainz) „Mysterium der Ethik“ vs. „corpus mysticum“ – Moralitätsverständnis bei Schopenhauer und Kant - Katerina Mihaylova (MLU HalleWittenberg) Kant über die moralische Qualität physischer Selbsterhaltung als Kritik an Stoa und die Gegenkritik durch Jakob Friedrich Fries <p>- 18:00 Empfang im Rathaus der Stadt Halle an der Saale / Reception in the City Hall</p>	

of Halle an der Saale.

SAMSTAG / SATURDAY, 29. APRIL 2017

Sektionen / Parallel sessions.

09:00 –09:50

- Ubirajara Rancan de Azevedo Marques (Universidade Estadual Paulista, Campus de Marília) Uma anotação de Kant acerca dum exemplo musical de Eberhard sobre o 'fundamento das representações'
- Jörg Noller (LMU München) "Practical Reason is not the Will": Kant and Reinhold's Dilemma
- Mònica Carbó Ribugent (Univ. Girona) On Beauty, Truth and Philosophy: Kantian aesthetical legacy

09:55 – 10:45

- Fernando M. F. Silva (Univ. Lisboa) Novalis, Critic of Kant
- Antonino Falduto (MLU HalleWittenberg) Reinhold and Kant on Freedom and the Evil
- Anna-Maria C. Bartsch (LMU Univ. München) Kants ästhetische Urteilstheorie und die Kritik der Formalen Ästhetik nach Zimmermann

11:15 – 12:05

- Falk Wunderlich (MLU HalleWittenberg) Kant and Schulze: The challenge of direct realism
- Fernando Moledo (Univ. Buenos Aires) Der kantische Begriff der Menschenwürde
- Ansgar Lyssy (LMU München) Der Despot als philosophisches Problem – Friedrich Bouterweks Kritik an Kants politischer Philosophie

12:10 – 13:00

- Zdravko Kobe (Univ. Ljubljana) Kant und seine Kritiker. Der Fall Jacob Sigismund Beck
- Maria de Lourdes Borges (Univ. Santa Catarina) The feminist criticism of Kant's philosophy
- Esther Oluffa Pedersen (Roskilde Univ.) The Deluged heart of the Idle Cosmopolite is a Dwelling for Nobody. How Herder urged Kant to think through teleology

15:00 - 19.00 Kulturprogramm / Cultural Programme: Franckesche Stiftungen.

19.00 Heiner F. Klemme, Corey Dyck, Falk Wunderlich et al: „ Philosophy in Halle (1696 -): A Hotspot of Enlightenment“.

CHRISTIAN-WOLFF-HAUS, Große Märkerstraße 10, Halle an der Saale.

In cooperation with „Christian-Wolff-Gesellschaft für die Philosophie der Aufklärung / Christian-Wolff-Society for the Philosophy of the Enlightenment“.

Empfang / Reception.

SONNTAG / SUNDAY, 30. APRIL 2017

Sektionen / Parallel sessions.

09:00 –09:50

- Kurt Röttgers (FernUniv. Hagen) Frühe Kant-Kritik von der Sprachlichkeit her
- Roberto R. Aramayo (IFS-CSIC, Madrid) Is Diderot perhaps an unknown Newton of politics for Kant? The History of the Two Indies and Kantian political thought
- Manja Kisner (LMU München) Fichtes metaphysische Rezeption des kantischen transzendentalen Idealismus

09:55 – 10:45

- Thomas Sören Hoffmann (FernUniv. Hagen) Kritik und Metakritik: Zu Hamanns

CON-TEXTOS KANTIANOS

International Journal of Philosophy

N.º 5, Junio 2017, pp. 508-535

ISSN: 2386-7655

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.805921

Kantlektüren

- Luigi Caranti (Univ. Catania) The Kantian Federation and its critics
- Dietmar Heidemann (Univ. Luxemburg) Hegels Kritik an Kants Ding an sich in der ‚Wissenschaft der Logik‘

11:05 – 11:55

- Ileana Beade (Univ. Buenos Aires) Some observations regarding Hamann’s critique of Kant’s distinction between the public and the private use of reason
- Nuria Sánchez Madrid (Univer. Complutense Madrid) Kantian vs. Current Defenses of Human Rights: Some Critical Remark
- Sandra Viviana Palermo (Univ. Buenos Aires) Dell’unità dello scopo. La critica di Hegel in Fede e sapere alla lettura kantiana di Spinoza nella Critica del giudizio

12:00 – 12:50

- Saneyuki Yamatsuta (Univ. Tokyo) Subjektivität oder Intersubjektivität? Tetsuro Watsujis Kritik der kantischen Ethik
- Anselmo Aportone (Univ. Roma Tor Vergata) Synthesis bei Kant und Strawson
- Luca Fonnesu (Univ. Pavia) Die Kritik der Kantischen Prinzipienethik bei Fichte und Hegel

14:00 – 14:50 Uhr

- Fuling Wang (Renmin Univ., Beijing) Kant’s philosophy in the perspective of Confucianism: take Mou Zongsan’s thought as an example
- Tomasz Kupś (Univ. Toruń) Institutioneller Antikantianismus an der Kaiserlichen Universität Vilnius. Wettbewerb an dem PhilosophieLehrstuhl in den Jahren 1821-1822
- Martin Sticker (Trinity College Dublin) Common Human Reason and the Fact of Reason

14.55 – 15.45

- Natalia Danilkina (OZSW, Univ. of Groningen) The revival of natural Law in Russia
- Jitka Paitlová (Univ. Pilsen) Karl Poppers Kritik an Kant
- Jacinto Rivera de Rosales (Univ. E. D., Madrid) Die Kritiken des neuen Realismus an Kant

16:00 – 16:50

- Alexei Krouglov (Univ. Moskau) Kants Kritik von Vladimir Solowjow
- Irene Breuer (Bergische Univ. Wuppertal) Kant und Husserl: Ding an sich und Telos des Erfahrungsprozesses
- Tinca Prunea-Bretonnet (Univ. Bucharest) From mysticism to metaphysics: Kant and his critics in the last decades of the 19th century

16:55 – 17:45

- Sandra Zákutná (Univ. Prešov) The Reception and Criticism of Kant’s Philosophy in the Region of Today’s Slovakia at the Turn of the 18th Century and in the First Half of the 19th Century
- Hsin-pai Chen (EberhardKarls-Univ. Tübingen) Abschied von Kant? - Ulrich Klugs Kritik und die Rolle des Wiedervergeltungsrechts in Kants Rechtsdenken
- Bernd Dörflinger (Univ. Trier) Gerold Prauss’ Kritik an der Linienanalogie in Kants Zeittheorie

17:50 – 18:40

- Marita Rainsborough (Univ. Hamburg / Univ. Kiel) Kant revisited. Die kritische Auseinandersetzung mit Kants Universalismus und Kosmopolitismus in der afrikanischen Philosophie

- Gabriele Tomasi (Univ. Padova) On Greenberg on Kant and the common sense
 - Günter Zöller (LMU Univ. München) Plato on Revolution. Political Conservatism in Kant and J. G. Schlosser
- 19:30 Kulturprogramm / Cultural programme.

Aarhus Kant Week 2017	
Speaker:	James Conant (University of Chicago)
Master Class:	Why Kant is not a Kantian
Lugar:	Aarhus University, Søauditorierne, William Scharff Auditoriet
Fecha:	8 – 9/5/2017
Información:	– Organizadores: The Kant Research Group at Aarhus University
<p>The course seeks to show how a proper understanding of the structure of the B Deduction—the philosophical lynchpin of Kant's <i>Critique of Pure Reason</i>—reveals its aim to be one of making sense of our capacities for sensibility and understanding in the light of each other: each is shown to depend on its relation to the other to be the sort of faculty that it is in a finite rational being.</p> <p>All are welcome. Graduate students and young researchers are particularly encouraged to attend. Registration is required. Please send your name and university affiliation to: KantWeek2017@gmail.com</p>	
Public Lecture:	Kant's Critique of the Layer-Cake Conception of the Mind
Lugar:	Aarhus University, Søauditorierne, Jeppe Vontilius Auditoriet (1252-310)
Fecha:	10/5/2017, 11:15-13:00
All are welcome. No registration required.	
International Workshop:	Transcendental Idealism and Scepticism – New Perspectives
Fecha:	11 - 12/5/2017, 09:30-18:15
Lugar:	11/5/2017 Jeppe Vontilius Auditoriet (1252-310) 12/5/2017 Merete Barker Auditoriet (1253-211) Søauditorierne, Aarhus University
Keynote speakers:	James Conant (University of Chicago), Carsten Fogh Nielsen (Aarhus University), Anil Gomes (Oxford), Dietmar Heidemann (University of Luxembourg), Guido Kreis (Aarhus University), Lars Lodberg (Aarhus University), Jacob Lautrup Kristensen (University of Oslo), Jessica Leech (King's College, London), Camilla Serck-Hansen (University of Oslo), Andrew Stephenson (Aarhus University)
<p>In his <i>Critique of Pure Reason</i>, Kant established a groundbreaking new position which he called “Transcendental Idealism”. One of the main aims of the transcendental arguments contained in the <i>Critique</i> is a successful refutation of modern forms of scepticism. The international workshop wants to shed light on transcendental idealism and its anti-sceptical potential from new perspectives.</p> <p>All are welcome. No registration required.</p>	
Información:	http://conferences.au.dk/KantWeek2017/

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ISSN: 2386-7655

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.805921

Kant: Action, Knowledge, Belief	
Fecha:	25 – 27/05/2017
Lugar:	Department of Philosophy American University of Beirut Beirut, Lebanon
Información:	www.kantataub.weebly.com – Sponsor: Goethe Institute, Beirut
Keynote speakers:	Andrew Chignell (Cornell University), Pauline Kleingeld (University of Groningen), Konstantin Pollok (University of South Carolina), Nicholas Stang (University of Toronto)
<p>The Department of Philosophy, in collaboration with CVSP and the Goethe Institute, will host the first international conference in Lebanon on the philosophy of Immanuel Kant. The conference will bring together eminent scholars from Europe, United States and the region to speak on one of four themes: Kant and the Philosophy of Action, Kant and the Philosophy of Science, Kant and the Philosophy of Religion, or the reception of Kant’s philosophy in the Middle East. These themes have been chosen to allow for papers on the usual areas in Kant scholarship, while also encouraging those that relate Kant’s philosophy to contemporary work. In particular, the inclusion of a session on the reception of Kant’s philosophy in the Middle East is intended to foster exchange between scholars of the region and our international guests. A fourth day (May 28th) will be devoted to an excursion to one or more of the many historical sites in Lebanon for participants who would like to attend.</p>	
CFP:	<p>Deadline: 1/03/2017</p> <p>We are now inviting abstracts of <u>no more than 500 words</u> for papers of 30 minutes in length on any of the themes above. The deadline for submissions is March 1st.</p> <p>Please send abstracts to: kantataub@gmail.com.</p>
Nota:	<p>Free or budget accommodation for early-career researchers, graduate students or others in need may be available upon request. Please contact the organizers for further information. Details about travel within Lebanon and local accommodation will soon be available on the conference website above.</p>

Philosophical Controversies and <i>Preisfragen</i>: Shaping the Enlightenment between Wolff and Kant	
Fecha:	18 – 19/05/2017
Lugar:	ICUB, University of Bucharest; New Europe College Plantelor 21 București 023971 Romania
Información:	https://irhunibuc.wordpress.com/philosophical-controversies-and-preisfragen-shaping-the-enlightenment-between-wolff-and-kant-18-19-may-2017 – Organizadores: Tinca Prunea-Bretonnet (University of Bucharest)
Keynote speakers:	Paola Basso (Bucharest), Karin de Boer (Leuven), Vlad Dolghi (Bucharest), Daniel Dumouchel (Montreal), Corey Dyck (Western Ontario), Matteo Favaretti Camposampiero (Venice), Ursula Goldenbaum (Atlanta), Sophie Grapotte (Lyon), Norbert Hinske (Trier), Christian Leduc (Montreal), Alessandro Nannini (Jena), Elena Partene (Paris), Tinca Prunea-Bretonnet (Bucharest), Andrea Reichenberger (Paderborn).
<p>The conference examines the impact of a series of key debates on the development of German Enlightenment philosophy from Wolff to Kant. It discusses the ways in which these controversies both responded to problems inherited from the seventeenth century and contributed to the formation of a distinctive German philosophical discourse. Special attention is paid to the ‘speculative philosophy class’ of the Berlin Academy, which through its prize essay contests both substantially enhanced the significance of ongoing controversies and initiated new debates, often taking its cue from the philosophical positions of Leibniz, Wolff, the British empiricists, Newton, and Kant. The conference papers cover both theoretical approaches to the art of debating and specific debates in the fields of metaphysics, the philosophy of science, psychology, aesthetics, and epistemology. They will address the following questions: What was the debates’ impact on eighteenth-century German philosophy? What role did the enlightened public play in these controversies? In the end, did the controversies leave the key questions open or succeeded in reaching some agreement? To what extent was the German Enlightenment driven by antagonism – in particular, can we detect a shift from agonistic arguments in the first half of the century to a more conciliatory debate mood in the second half?</p>	
<p>PROGRAM:</p> <p>Thursday, 18 May</p> <p>10.00-10.10 Welcome: Tinca Prunea-Bretonnet 10.10-11.00 Norbert Hinske (Trier): Baumeisters Abhandlung über die wichtigsten Kontroversen der neueren Philosophie</p> <p>11.00-11.20 Coffee</p> <p>11.20-12.10 Corey Dyck (London, Canada): The Leibniz/Clarke Correspondence and Wolff’s Turn to Ontology 12.10-13.00 Matteo Favaretti Camposampiero (Venice): Incompatible Immortalities: Debates</p>	

on the Afterlife in the Wolffian Age

13.00-14.30 Lunch

14.30-15.20 Andrea Reichenberger (Paderborn): The Concept of Inertia from Newton to Kant

15.20-16.10 Christian Leduc (Montreal): Kant on Mechanism in the 1750s

16.10-16.40 Coffee

16.40-17.30 Vlad Dolghi (Bucharest): Maupertuis on the Laws of Nature

17.30-18.20 Alessandro Nannini (Jena): Imperium non tyrannis. The Controversy on Sensibility at the Origins of Modern Aesthetics

Friday, 19 May

10.00-10.50 Ursula Goldenbaum (Atlanta): The Public Scandal about the Judgement of the Berlin Academy concerning a Leibniz Letter

10.50-11.20 Coffee

11.20-12.10 Daniel Dumouchel (Montreal): En amont du concours de 1777: Sulzer sur la connaissance et le sentiment

12.10-13.00 Paola Basso (Bucharest): Geometry and Theology: The Climax of the Battle for the "Primacy of Certainty" during the Preisfrage for 1763

13.00-14.30 Lunch

14.30-15.20 Karin de Boer (Leuven): Kant's Inquiries into a New Touchstone for Metaphysical Truths

15.20-16.10 Elena Partene (Paris): La crise de la métaphysique et la critique du paradigme logico-mathématique

16.10-16.40 Coffee

16.40-17.30 Tinca Prunea-Bretonnet (Bucharest): Metaphysics in the Kantian Age: Progress or Decline?

17.30-18.20 Sophie Grapotte (Lyon): Le suprasensible dans la réponse de Kant à la Preisfrage pour l'année 1791

Nota:

The conference is organized within the framework of the research project *Philosophy between Mathematical Method and Experiment: the Berlin Academy (1746-1764)*, funded by UEFISCDI-CNCS (PN-RU-TE-II 2014-4-2522).

Leuven Kant Conference 2017	
Fecha:	1 – 2/06/2017
Lugar:	Institute of Philosophy University of Leuven Huis Bethlehem, Schapenstraat 34, Leuven, Belgium
Información:	Program, registration and practical information: http://hiw.kuleuven.be/eng/events/leuvenkantconference Contact: leuvenkantconference@kuleuven.be – Organizadores: Karin de Boer, Arnaud Pelletier, Simon Truwant, Dennis Vanden Auweele
Keynote speakers:	Jeanine Grenberg (St. Olaf College) Julia Jansen (KU Leuven) Konstantin Pollok (University of South Carolina)
<p>Dealing with almost all areas of research, including metaphysics, epistemology, the natural sciences, mathematics, ethics, aesthetics, theology, history, anthropology, and politics, Kant's works had a great impact on developments within and outside philosophy in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. However, certain themes, such as Kant's philosophy of religion or his pre-critical works, are rather seldom discussed outside of specialized workshops. The relationship between the various aspects of Kant's philosophy likewise receives little attention. We believe that researchers working on certain elements of Kant's thought could profit greatly from exchanges with researchers working within a different tradition or on different topics. It is the aim of the Leuven Kant Conference to enhance such exchanges.</p>	
CFP:	<p>Deadline: 5/01/2017</p> <p>The Institute of Philosophy of the University of Leuven invites submissions for the fourth Leuven Kant Conference. Papers are welcome on any aspect of Kant's philosophy. The conference aims at stimulating fruitful exchanges between established scholars, young researchers, and PhD students. Presentation time will be 25 minutes + 20 minutes for discussion.</p> <p>Abstracts (no more than 500 words) should be sent in MSWord as attachment to leuvenkantconference@kuleuven.be</p> <p>Abstracts should be prepared for double-blind review by removing any identification details. The author's name, paper title, institutional position and affiliation, as well as contact information, should be included in the body of the e-mail.</p> <p>Notification of acceptance by February 1, 2017.</p>
Nota:	The conference fee (including coffee and lunch breaks) is €10 for both days (without conference dinner) or €55 (with conference dinner).

Visual Reasoning and Intuition in Mathematics. From Kant's Euclidicity to Digitalization	
Fecha:	29/06 – 1/07/2017
Lugar:	Institut für Philosophie, Freie Universität Berlin Souterrain Habelschwerdter Allee 30 Berlin 14195 Germany
Keynote Speakers:	Pirmin Stekeler-Weithofer (Universität Leipzig), Kenneth Manders (University of Pittsburgh), Marcus Giaquinto (University College London), Benedikt Löwe (ILLC Amsterdam/Universität Hamburg), Sybille Krämer (FU Berlin), Ladislav Kvasz (Charles University, Prague), Konrad Polthier (FU Berlin), Valeria Giardino (Henri Poincaré Archives, Nancy), Brendan Larvor (University of Hertfordshire), Vincenzo De Risi (Universität Leipzig), Ofra Rechter (Tel Aviv University), Silvia De Toffoli (Stanford University/IHPST Paris), Jan Wöpping (Forschungsverbund Berlin), Özge Ekin (FU Berlin), Martin Beck (FU Berlin)
Información:	http://www.geisteswissenschaften.fu-berlin.de/we01/media/Flyer_Visual-Reasoning.pdf – Sponsor: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) – Organizadores: Martin Beck (Freie Universität Berlin) Ozge Ekin (Freie Universität Berlin) Solvej Hartmann (Freie Universität Berlin) Sybille Krämer (Freie Universität Berlin)
Is mathematics only about proof? In search for its foundation, mathematics was often conceived as a hierarchic and uniform edifice of ideas. A praxeological view reverses this image. It considers a plurality of mathematical practices from heuristics and problem solving to communication. It reveals a historic and pragmatic diversity of approaches and media of mathematical thinking. This international conference is conceived as a contribution to a praxeological philosophy of mathematics. It focuses on practices that include visualization and intuition.	

Kant on Sex, Love and Friendship	
Fecha:	21 – 23/07/2017
Lugar:	Department of Philosophy, University of St. Andrews
Información:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sponsors: Scots Philosophical Association Mind Association Aristotelian Society UK Kant Society – Organisers: Martin Brecher (Universität Bonn) Pärttyli Rinne (University of St Andrews) Jens Timmermann (University of St Andrews)
Speakers:	Martin Brecher (Bonn/Mannheim), Melissa Fahmy (Georgia), Jeanine Grenberg (St Olaf College), Christoph Horn (Bonn), Robert Louden (Southern Maine), Kate Moran (Brandeis), Pärttyli Rinne (St Andrews), Dieter Schönecker (Siegen), Jens Timmermann (St Andrews), Michael Walschots (St Andrews).
<p>The basic aim of the conference is to understand how sex, love and friendship function in Kant’s philosophy, both individually and in conjunction with each other. While research on these issues has escalated in recent years, we still lack an inclusive outlook on the questions surrounding the concept of love, broadly conceived, in Kant. Even though Kant’s philosophy has been under vivid discussion for over 200 years, to our knowledge, nothing like ‘Kant on Sex, Love and Friendship’ has ever been organised.</p> <p>The concepts of sex, love and friendship are more pertinent to Kant than often thought. They play an integral role in his conception of human life. The three notions are closely interrelated, and to an extent, overlapping. In different parts of his philosophy, Kant acknowledges that from the crudest impulses of nature to the highest ideals of virtue and moral happiness, the phenomenon of love permeates human existence. In particular, an understanding of how sex, love and friendship function in Kant’s practical philosophy is necessary for a comprehensive understanding of his ethical project.</p> <p>The conference brings together a group of scholars and philosophers working on these topics to present their research, exchange and develop ideas, and to establish points of contact between their individual research approaches.</p>	

St Andrews Kant Reading Party 2017	
Fecha:	24 – 27/07/2017
Lugar:	Department of Philosophy, University of St. Andrews The Burn Edzell DD9 7YP United Kingdom
Información:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sponsors: British Society for the History of Philosophy International Society for Utilitarian Studies Mind Association Scots Philosophical Association Centre for Academic, Professional and Organisational Development, University of St Andrews UK Kant Society – Organisers: Stefano Lo Re (University of St Andrews) Lucas Sierra (University of St Andrews) Jens Timmermann (University of St Andrews)
<p>It is our pleasure to invite you to the 10th edition of the St Andrews Kant Reading Party. The event will take place between the 24th and the 27th of July 2017, at the Burn House in Edzell (http://theburn.goodenough.ac.uk/). The title of this year's edition is 'Kant and Sidgwick', and the main goal will be to investigate the philosophical relations between Kant's ethics and the utilitarian philosophy of Henry Sidgwick, with a special focus on the nature of morality and the good.</p> <p>It is commonly argued that Kantian ethics and Utilitarianism (whose most rigorous formulation is arguably to be found in the work of Henry Sidgwick) are incompatible and even opposed to each other. However, it has also been argued that the two views are actually quite similar, both in form and in upshot, and some philosophers have gone as far as to claim (i) that they are largely compatible and/or (ii) that by combining the two an even stronger ethical system could be developed. The debate over the relation between Kantian ethics and utilitarian philosophy is still alive and well, waiting for new insights and new creative contributions.</p> <p>This year there will be up to six discussion sessions (all texts will be made available), as well as up to four paper sessions (see CFA below).</p> <p>Participation Fees: Staff members: £150; Students: £75 The fee covers accommodation and full board at the Burn House, as well as transportation from St Andrews to the Burn House and back.</p> <p><u>Invited speakers will be waived the entire participation fee</u> (see CFA below). If you would like to attend but child care duties make it difficult, please get in contact with Lucas Sierra Vélez (lsv2@st-andrews.ac.uk). We will do our best to meet your requests, and we hope to be able to provide financial support.</p>	
Registration:	Since the number of places is limited, the registration process is divided in two steps: 1) Informal registration: send an e-mail

CON-TEXTOS KANTIANOS

International Journal of Philosophy

N.º 5, Junio 2017, pp. 508-535

ISSN: 2386-7655

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.805921

	<p>including name, affiliation, and a brief expression of interest to Lucas Sierra Vélez (lsv2@st-andrews.ac.uk) by the 16th of June.</p> <p>2) Payment: selected participants will be given instructions on how to make the online fee payment.</p>
<p>CFP:</p>	<p>Postgraduate students are invited to send anonymised abstracts of no longer than 750 words, as well as a separate cover sheet including name, position, institutional affiliation, and e-mail address to Kristina Kersa (kk203@st-andrews.ac.uk) by the 16th of June. Abstracts will be selected by blind review, and applicants will be notified by the 30th of June.</p> <p>Papers should be suitable for a presentation of 40 minutes, and should attempt to clarify the relations between Kant’s ethics and Sidgwick’s Utilitarianism, or at least between Kantian ethics and Utilitarianism more generally. Preference will be given to papers addressing topics from the following list:</p> <p>The nature of action, practical reason and morality; The nature of human agency and human motivation; The relation between maxims/motives/intentions and consequences; The Kantian idea of ‘practical love’ and its relation to utilitarian benevolence; The moral standing of non-human animals; The axiological, practical and moral significance of happiness; The nature of happiness; The meaning and varieties of ‘hedonism’; The Kantian highest good and its relation to the idea of a maximally happy world; The idea of ‘deserving happiness’; The dualism of practical reason (morality vs egoism); The question of the ultimate/supreme good; The meaning of the term ‘good’ and the varieties of goodness; The notions of intrinsic value and unconditional value; The concepts of ‘dignity’ and ‘respect’; The distinction between ‘harming someone’ and ‘wronging someone’; Ideal theory vs non-ideal theory; Self-regarding and other-regarding duties.</p> <p>For any questions, please do not hesitate to contact Lucas Sierra Vélez (lsv2@st-andrews.ac.uk).</p>

UK Kant Society - 2017 Annual Conference Kant and Contemporary Philosophy	
Fecha:	4 – 5/09/2017
Lugar:	Department of Philosophy, University of St. Andrews
Información:	https://ukks2017.wordpress.com/
Keynote speakers:	Lucy Allais (UCSD/Witwatersrand) Andrea Esser (Jena)
<p>It goes without saying that Kant's writings had an enormous impact on the debates of his time. To what extent, however, can Kant's thought still contribute to contemporary, 21st century philosophical discussions? Are his views no longer relevant, or does Kant still offer viable and defensible positions considered from a present-day point of view? Are there certain debates in contemporary philosophy where Kant's influence is particularly noticeable? To what degree do current 'Kantian' approaches to problems in metaphysics, ethics, etc. represent Kant's own position? This conference aims to explore and foster debate on the above and related questions, though papers on all themes related to Kant's philosophy are welcome.</p>	
CFP:	<p>Deadline: 01/06/2017</p> <p>Papers are invited from anyone interested in any aspect of Kant's philosophy, though submissions dealing specifically with the conference theme are encouraged. If you are interested in giving a presentation, please submit an abstract of 800-1000 words (prepared for blind review) to Michael Walschots at: ukks2017@gmail.com, and fill out the following online form:</p>
<p>https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1fPZhglEK_wa33D2zgeSKxjeKstioT9q5igoWbD17kGI/</p>	

Kant Section: "Kant on Political Change"	
European Consortium for Political Research General Conference (ECPR) 2017	
Fecha:	6 – 9/9/2017
Lugar:	University of Oslo, Norway
Información:	https://ecpr.eu/Events/SectionDetails.aspx?SectionID=687&EventID=96
"Rights and Duties in Kantian Political and Legal Philosophy"	
<i>Panel Chairs:</i> Alyssa R. Bernstein (Ohio University) and Christoph Hanisch (Ohio University)	
<i>Section:</i> “Kant on Political Change” (organized by the ECPR Kantian Standing Group)	
<i>Section Chairs:</i> Sorin Baiasu (Keele University) and Howard Williams (Aberystwyth University)	
<p>The recent wave of impressive Kant scholarship in political and legal philosophy has brought to the forefront a number of foundational issues, such as the nature of rights and the problem of political authority. We suggest discussing the current state of these debates by emphasizing a couple of specific questions: What exactly is the normative status of provisional rights in Kant’s pre-institutional state of nature? Is the notion of such rights coherent? If so, what are the implications of the normativity of such (natural?) rights for their ‘juridified siblings’ in the rightful condition? How should collective will-formation processes be constrained by these rights? In particular, what do these rights mean for the self-understanding of citizens in democratic republics and for their relationship to the modern state’s authority? Are Kant-inspired accounts of civil disobedience and political protest theoretically convincing and practically viable?</p> <p>In relation to jurisprudence and philosophy of law, and following Jeremy Waldron et al.’s lead, we are interested in investigating the question to what extent a Kantian framework is sympathetic to the sovereignty of democratic legislation or whether it rather supports strong judicial review. Hence, panel contributions attempting to systematize Kant’s jurisprudence in the light of contemporary legal philosophies (positivism, natural rights,...) are very much welcome. More generally, we seek contributions that reflect on the relationship between pre-institutional and legal rights that are sensitive to the intricacies that come with the contrast between ideal and non-ideal theorizing.</p>	
CFP:	Deadline: 6/02/2017 Please submit abstracts of no more than 400 words to: bernstei@ohio.edu and hanisch@ohio.edu

The Midwest Study Group of the North American Kant Society	
Fecha:	6 – 7/10/2017
Lugar:	Department of Philosophy, University of Minnesota Minneapolis 55455, United States
Información:	– Organizadores: Michael Bennett McNulty (University of Minnesota)
Keynote:	Daniel Warren (UC Berkeley)
CFP:	<p>Deadline: 30/06/2017</p> <p>The Midwest Study Group of NAKS invites submission for its Fall 2017 meeting to be held October 6-7th at University of Minnesota, Twin Cities (hosted by Michael Bennett McNulty). Submissions should be prepared for blind review. Please send contact information in a separate document, indicating whether you are a graduate student. Presentation time is limited to 25 minutes and submissions should not exceed 20 pages (double-spaced, regular margins).</p> <p>In addition, the program committee invites proposals for panel discussions on Kantian topics or author-meets-critics sessions on recently published books. Proposals should include a short (up to 500 words) description of the topic/summary of the book to be discussed, as well as brief biographies of the confirmed participants.</p> <p>The selection committee welcomes contributions on all topics of Kantian scholarship (both contemporary and historically oriented), including discussions of Kant's immediate predecessors and successors. We especially encourage submissions from individuals of groups underrepresented in philosophy and Kant scholarship in particular.</p> <p>The best graduate student paper will receive a \$200 stipend and be eligible for the <i>Markus Herz Prize</i> awarded by NAKS. Papers already presented at other NAKS study groups or meetings are not eligible for submission. Presenters must be members of NAKS in good standing (though this is not required in order to submit a paper).</p> <p>Papers should be submitted electronically (in .pdf or .docx format) to the Program Committee Chair, Corey W. Dyck (cdyck5@uwo.ca).</p> <p>For more information, contact Qiannan Li: lixx4920@umn.edu.</p>

North American Kant Society & the Society for German Idealism and Romanticism 2017 Joint Conference NAKS Biennial Conference and the SGIR Anual Conference	
Fecha:	14 – 15/10/2017
Lugar:	Department of Philosophy, Stanford University Stanford, United States
Información:	www.thesgir.org www.northamericankantsociety.onefireplace.org – Organizadores: Gerad Gentry Helga Varden
<p>This joint conference takes the place of the annual SGIR conference and the biennial NAKS conference. The theme for the conference will be <i>Kantian Legacies in German Idealism and Romanticism</i>.</p>	
CFP:	<p>Deadline: 1/05/2017</p> <p>The North American Kant Society and the Society for German Idealism and Romanticism are inviting submissions for the 2017 SGIR-NAKS joint conference to be held at Stanford University. The SGIR and NAKS welcome papers on all aspects of the philosophy of Kant and of the various figures in German Idealism and Romanticism generally. Preference will be given to talks that concern the relationship between Kant and some aspect of Idealism and Romanticism. Submissions should not exceed 5,000 words.</p> <p>Submitted papers will be considered for the following awards:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) SGIR Faculty Paper of the Year (2) SGIR Graduate Paper of the Year (3) NAKS Markus Herz Prize for graduate students. <p>Please email submissions to: sgir.naks.2017@gmail.com.</p> <p>Registration: http://www.thesgir.org/cfps---conference-announcements.html</p>

Premio / Prize

Premio Kant para Jóvenes Investigadores e Investigadoras en Lengua Española 2ª Convocatoria	
Información:	www.sekle.org
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Se concederá un premio y dos accésits (dos menciones) a artículos de investigación, inéditos y escritos en español sobre cualquier tema acerca del pensamiento y la filosofía de Kant. 2. Podrán participar investigadores que tengan menos de 40 años e investigadoras con menos de 43 el día de la convocatoria de este Premio, o sea, el 1 de febrero de 2017, excepto los miembros de la Junta Directiva de la SEKLE y de la Redacción de la REK. 3. Los artículos contarán con una extensión máxima de 80.000 caracteres, espacios incluidos. 4. Los originales serán enviados hasta el domingo día 11 de febrero de 2018 (inclusive) a la dirección electrónica: segundopremiokantsekle@gmail.com, con un documento oficial (carnet de identidad o pasaporte) escaneado que atestigüe la edad del concursante. 5. Estos originales serán recogidos por el Secretario de la SEKLE. Sólo él conocerá el nombre de los autores. La evaluación de los originales se efectuará de manera anónima. 6. El Jurado estará compuesto por tres miembros nombrados por la Junta Directiva. Su composición se dará a conocer el día 12 de enero de 2018. 7. En los artículos presentados se valorarán la solidez y coherencia de la argumentación, la originalidad y el conocimiento de la obra de Kant. Este premio podrá quedar desierto a juicio del Jurado. Su fallo será inapelable. 8. El premio consistirá en la entrega de 1.000 euros. Además, el artículo premiado y los dos accésits o menciones serán publicados en la Revista de Estudios Kantianos de la SEKLE, haciéndose allí referencia a dicho galardón. 9. Se hará entrega del premio en el marco de un congreso de la SEKLE. En esta segunda edición eso tendrá lugar durante el congreso de octubre de 2018 en Valencia (España). 10. Este Premio Kant se convocará cada dos años. 	
CFP:	Deadline: 11/02/2018

Exposición / Exhibition

Umwege. Annäherungen an Immanuel Kant in Wien, in Österreich und in Osteuropa	
Fecha:	19/10/2016 – 2/12/2016
Lugar:	Alpen-Adria-Universität Klagenfurt Bibliothek, 1. Stock Universitätsstr. 65-67 Klagenfurt am Wörthersee 9020 Austria
Información:	– Organizador: Ritter Bernhard (AAU Klagenfurt) Herzog Christa (AAU Klagenfurt, Universitätsbibliothek)
Keynote speakers:	Sauer Werner (Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz)
Anlässlich des Internationalen Kant-Kongresses 2015 wurde in Wien die Ausstellung "Umwege. Annäherungen an Immanuel Kant in Wien, in Österreich und in Osteuropa" konzipiert. Im Sommersemester 2016 wurde sie an der Universität Graz gezeigt; jetzt kommt sie nach Klagenfurt – in Kooperation mit der Ausstellungsreihe "Kostbarkeiten aus der Bibliothek" und ergänzt um den Bezug zur Geschichte des Kärntner Herbert-Kreises. Prof. Werner Sauer von der Karl-Franzens-Universität Graz wird mit einem Vortrag über die Rolle des Herbert-Kreises in der Geschichte des Frühkantianismus in die Ausstellung einführen.	

PARERGA KANTIANA
II ENCUENTRO INTERNACIONAL CTK / CTK E-Books
<https://www.con-textoskantianos.net/index.php/revista>

Madrid, 29-30 de Mayo de 2017
Instituto de Filosofía del Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (IFS-CSIC)
Facultad de Filosofía de la Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM)

Coordinadores:
Roberto R. Aramayo (IFS-CSIC)
Concha Roldán (Directora del Instituto de Filosofía del CSIC)
Nuria Sánchez Madrid (UCM)
José Luis Villacañas (Director del Departamento de Historia de la Filosofía de la UCM)

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